

TITLE: Clinical implications of Extracellular Vesicles in Pancreatic Cancer: from biomarkers to novel magic bullets.

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Abstract

Pancreatic cancer is a highly lethal and metastatic malignancy, mainly because is detected in advanced stages due to the limitations of current diagnostic methods when currently available therapies are ineffective. Therefore, the identification of useful biomarkers for early diagnosis and new therapeutic targets for pancreatic cancer is imperative. Recently, extracellular vesicles have emerged as promising biomarkers for the diagnosis and prognosis of pancreatic cancer. Given their presence in various bodily fluids, extracellular vesicles offer a non-invasive approach through liquid biopsy to detect and monitor cancer progression. In this review, we comprehensively examine the multifaceted roles of extracellular vesicles in the progression of cancer, while also exploring their potential as diagnostic, prognostic, and therapeutic biomarkers in the context of pancreatic cancer.

Keywords: extracellular vesicles, pancreatic cancer, liquid biopsy, diagnosis biomarkers.

Introduction

As of today, cancer is one of the leading causes of death worldwide. In 2020 alone, more than 19 million new cases were diagnosed and almost 10 million people died from cancer. Pancreatic cancer (PC) has become the seventh leading cause of cancer deaths globally, with nearly 500,000 deaths in 2020^[1]. Mortality data related to PC in Europe in 2020 is indeed alarming. During that year, 132,134 individuals succumbed to PC, representing 29% of the total fatalities due to cancer in Europe. Furthermore, the incidence of PC in Europe is notably elevated, with a rate of 2.31 per 100,000 inhabitants, and a total of 140,116 new cases diagnosed within the same year^[2], representing a mortality rate of 94%.

The high mortality rate of PC is largely attributed to the challenges of early diagnosis. It is well-established that PC tends to remain asymptomatic during its early stages or presents symptoms that are often subtle and inconspicuous to patients. Consequently, its detection is frequently delayed until advanced stages, when its highly metastatic nature has led to widespread invasion of the body^[3].

Traditionally, PC detection has relied primarily on diagnostic methods involving tissue biopsies^[4] and imaging techniques such as Computed Tomography (CT), Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), Positron Emission Tomography (PET), and Endoscopic Ultrasonography (EUS)^[5]. Nonetheless, these methods come with inherent disadvantages, including high cost, radiation exposure risk, invasiveness, and the

potential for disease dissemination. Furthermore, they are time-consuming, not easily repeatable, and do not provide a comprehensive representation of the tumor microenvironment^[4,5] or tumor evolution.

To overcome these drawbacks, liquid biopsies have been developed^[4]. These diagnostic approaches facilitate the identification and monitoring of tumor progression through non-invasive sampling of body fluids like blood, serum, plasma, urine, or saliva. These fluids contain various components that can be harnessed for cancer diagnosis, including circulating tumor cells (CTCs), platelets, circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA), free RNA and extracellular vesicles (EVs)^[4,6].

Among these components, EVs have demonstrated significant potential as diagnostic markers in various cancers, as they serve as key mediators of intercellular communication in both normal and pathological contexts. EVs carry diverse cargo (proteins, lipids, nucleic acids, metabolites, etc.) that reflect the state of the cell of origin, which is invaluable for cancer detection^[7,8]. Specifically, in the context of PC, EVs may contain factors that promote and modulate tumor growth, angiogenesis, metastasis, and chemoresistance^[7]. Given their pivotal role in PC progression, both EVs and their contents can serve as biomarkers for this pathology.

This review aims to outline diverse methodologies used for the study and characterization of EVs, and their role as drivers of tumor development in PC. Additionally, it seeks to assess the potential of EVs as diagnostic, prognostic and therapeutic biomarkers for PC.

1. What are EVs?

EVs are nano- or micrometer-sized lipid vesicles secreted by the majority of both healthy and pathological cells^[4]. This diverse group of vesicles includes various subtypes primarily categorized by their biogenesis and size, namely: exosomes (EXOs) (30-150 nm), microvesicles (MVs) (150-1000 nm) and apoptotic bodies (ApoBDs) (1000-5000 nm)^[7].

EXOs biogenesis occurs through the endosomal pathway (Figure 1A). The process involves endocytosis, leading to the internalization of various cargoes, such as lipids, cytoplasmic or membrane proteins and nucleic acids^[9]. This internalization results in the formation of early endosomes (ESEs), which then mature into late endosomes (LSEs). These late endosomes generate multivesicular endosomes (MVBs). Following a second process of plasma membrane invagination, MVBs give rise to intraluminal vesicles (ILVs), which will later become EXOs. The fate of MVBs varies, as they can fuse with

lysosomes, autophagosomes, or the plasma membrane. In the latter case, exosomes enclosed in MVBs are released into the extracellular medium^[9].

The biogenesis of MVs is not as well characterized as that of EXOs. It is known to stem from the evagination of the plasma membrane (Figure 1A). In the other hand, apoptotic bodies are formed during apoptosis, a programmed cell death process. Similar to MVs, apoptotic bodies are released into the extracellular space through evagination (Figure 1B)^[10].

Under normal physiological conditions, all types of cells release EVs into the extracellular space, where they perform various functions, including cellular communication (autocrine, paracrine and/or endocrine signaling) and immune regulation^[4,10]. As a result, they can be found in different biological fluids such as blood, saliva and urine^[10].

2. EVs Isolation and Characterization methodologies.

To assess the potential of EVs as diagnostic and prognostic markers in PC, it is essential to have a comprehensive understanding of the most commonly utilized techniques for isolating and characterizing EVs from biological fluids. This review will particularly emphasize methodologies that enable the isolation of EVs from plasma or serum derived from blood samples.

In the absence of a standardized method for isolating EVs, the scientific community has proposed a wide range of techniques to accomplish this objective (Figure 2). Firstly, we will discuss isolation methods based on the density of EVs, such as ultracentrifugation (UC) and density gradient (DG) centrifugation. UC is the most frequently utilized technique due to its exceptional reproducibility and capacity to process considerable sample volumes. Nevertheless, it is not without limitations, given its high costs and time-consuming procedures. Furthermore, there is a potential risk of contamination with particles sharing similar density with EVs, such as lipoproteins. Additionally, the elevated centrifugal forces necessary in UC can negatively affect the integrity of EVs^[4]. In a similar context, protocols involving differential centrifugation followed by an UC step have been developed to distinguish between MVs and EXOs^[11].

On the other hand, DG centrifugation employs iodixanol or sucrose gradients for isolating EVs. However, albeit with comparable drawbacks to UC. Integration of both methods has demonstrated effectiveness to reduce contamination by proteins co-isolated with EVs^[12]. While DG provides higher yields compare to alternative techniques, its clinical

applicability is limited due to the extended procedure duration and the elevated equipment costs involved^[13].

Secondly, there are isolation methods based on the size of EVs: ultrafiltration (UF), Size Exclusion Chromatography (SEC) and Field Flow Fractionation (FFF). UF employs membranes with pore sizes ranging from 10 to 100 kDa. While UF is faster and less expensive than UC, it does have its disadvantages. For instance, membrane saturation can diminish isolation efficiency as the binding of EVs to the membrane may decrease the number of isolated EVs. Additionally, particles of a similar size to EVs can traverse the membrane, leading to sample contamination^[4,6].

In contrast to UC, SEC preserves the structure of EVs and prevents aggregation. However, particles of a similar size may still elute alongside EVs^[4]. An example of this is the higher levels of APOB and APOE found after isolation with SEC compared to those obtained with UC. Moreover, the use of SEC involves sample dilution, requiring an additional concentration step^[12].

Finally, isolation by FFF relies on the different diffusion coefficients of small and large particles, resulting in the elution of smaller particles (contaminating proteins) before larger ones (EVs). The main drawback is the reduced sample volume that can be processed^[6].

The utilization of precipitation techniques represents another widely adopted method due to its cost-effectiveness in comparison to the methods mentioned earlier. Notably, precipitation using hydrophilic polymer solutions, such as PEG, holds significance. This compound extracts water from the sample, thereby diminishing the solubility of EVs and facilitating their precipitation. An alternative approach for EVs precipitation involves the use of organic solvents like sodium acetate or protamine^[4]. Both methods offer potential application in clinical settings, as they are straightforward, direct and do not compromise the structural integrity of EVs^[4,13]. Nevertheless, they present certain limitations, including the risk of contamination through the co-precipitation of viruses and proteins, challenges associated with the removal of the precipitating agent from the sample and the potential interaction with the sample^[6,13].

Recently, commercial kits such as ExoQuick™ and ExoPrep™ have been introduced to efficiently isolate EVs from clinical serum and urine samples. However, these kits are relatively expensive, may still introduce contamination and are primarily optimized for isolating EXOs. Consequently, their effectiveness in isolating MVs and apoptotic bodies is limited^[4].

Similarly, there are techniques that rely on the selectivity and specificity of interactions between molecules present on the membrane of EVs and immobilized receptors on a surface (e.g., antibodies) such as magnetic beads or chromatographic columns^[6]. These methods include immunoprecipitation assays^[4], ELISA, affinity chromatography and others^[6]. Typically, these approaches employ antibodies targeting common EV surface markers such as anti-CD9, anti-CD63, anti-CD81, or EpCAM^[4]. Despite their high sensitivity, these techniques often suffer from low yields, thereby limiting their clinical applicability^[6].

In recent years, alternative methods have emerged, offering the promise of being faster and more cost-effective than traditional approaches. Examples include the nano-plasmonic exosome sensor (nPES) technique and affinity-based kits like ExoEasy™. In nPES, EVs are captured using surface-immobilized anti-CD81 antibodies on a sensor chip. To enhance sensitivity and specificity in isolation, two additional types of antibodies, anti-CD63 and anti-CD9, both specific to EVs, are used and hybridized with distinct nanoparticle probes (AuR and AuS). This method has several advantages, as it allows starting from minimal volumes of plasma samples without the need for pre-processing. Moreover, it offers rapid and highly sensitive EV detection, with a detection limit of 0.23 ng/μL^[14].

Beyond antibodies, other molecules, such as heparin, demonstrate an affinity for EVs. For instance, Balaj *et al.* aimed to compare the efficiency of UC for isolating EVs from plasma with an alternative approach involving UF followed by an affinity assay utilizing heparin immobilized on beads^[15]. Their study concluded that this novel protocol achieved EV isolation with morphology similar to that obtained via UC, with a reduced degree of protein co-isolation. Consequently, this method has proven highly effective for EVs isolation from biological fluids, including plasma.

Finally, microfluidic devices represent an innovative technique facilitating the capture of EVs using a network of microchannels that incorporate various isolation strategies based on properties such as affinity (antibodies immobilized on beads) or size (filtration, dielectrophoresis)^[4,6]. Notably, studies have been conducted with microfluidic devices incorporating a dielectrophoresis system to isolate EVs in blood samples from patients with PC^[4]. To enhance specificity, these devices integrate an immunofluorescence system for detecting specific markers on these EVs. This technique offers several advantages for clinical applications, demanding minimal sample volume and operates automatically. However, being a relatively recent method, it requires translational studies to establish its true utility and reliability as a diagnostic technique^[4].

After the isolation of EVs has been performed, purification and characterization become imperative to confirm their adequate isolation. The key parameters typically employed for EVs characterization are the number, size, concentration, morphology and markers associated with them^[4].

The most commonly utilized methods for quantifying the number, concentration and size of EVs are Nanoparticle Tracking Analysis (NTA) and Tunable Resistive Pulse Sensing (TRPS). NTA operates on the principle of differentiating the Brownian motion of each individual particle^[4]. It exhibits accuracy in detecting particles with diameters ranging from 30 nm to 1000 nm in solutions with concentrations ranging from 10^8 to 10^9 particles/ml. However, factors such as contamination by co-isolated proteins can introduce precision limitations in the counting process^[6].

On the other hand, TRPS detects the pulses generated by each particle in the solution under specified voltage and pressure conditions^[4]. Despite its high sensitivity, recent alternative methods aim to enhance the sensitivity of EV detection for particles with diameters below 50 nm and simplify sample preparation^[10]. These alternatives include techniques like nanoscale flow cytometry, surface plasmon resonance (SPR) and surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS). Although these methods hold promise for enhanced efficiency, their practical applicability in clinical settings remains to be determined^[10].

In contrast, the morphology of EVs is typically evaluated using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) or transmission electron microscopy (TEM). It is important to note, however, that the morphology of EVs can be affected by this methodology^[4].

An alternative approach for characterizing EVs involves the analysis of associated markers. The choice of technique depends on the type of marker, whether it's a protein, nucleic acids, or lipid^[10]. The detection of protein markers can be performed using techniques such as BCA, ELISA, Western Blot (WB), or flow cytometry. BCA offers the advantage of being cost-effective and rapid; however, its reliability hinges on prior sample purification. Conversely, the WB technique is unique in its ability to detect both intracellular and membrane proteins^[4]. Unfortunately, it exhibits lower sensitivity and requires an extended sample preparation process, which challenges the clinical applications^[10]. For cancer diagnosis, ELISA is often the most suitable method due to its high sensitivity, even with unpurified biological fluid samples^[4].

Regarding nucleic acids, DNA or RNA, their detection can be achieved through methods such as PCR, RT-qPCR, microarrays or sequencing techniques like NGS.

Detecting lipid markers within EVs, this task is a more complex task for several reasons. Firstly, there is limited knowledge concerning the composition and lipid ratios in EV membranes. Additionally, the high concentration of lipid particles in biological fluids can introduce challenges in detecting lipids associated with EVs. Furthermore, there are limited tools available for lipidomics studies, making mass spectrometry (MS) the primary viable option^[10].

Upon analyzing these techniques, we conclude that, despite the availability of a wide array of methods for isolating and characterizing EVs, many present challenges when implemented in clinical settings. Furthermore, these techniques frequently yield results with high variability. Consequently, there is a need for the establishment of standardized methodologies that are not only sensitive but also user-friendly and accessible for clinical applications.

3. The relationship between EVs and Pancreatic Cancer

As is well known, tumor progression is not directed exclusively by the tumor cells themselves. Numerous cell types play a role in its expansion. The tumor microenvironment (TME) surrounding the tumor is composed of fibroblasts, endothelial cells and cells of the immune system such as lymphocytes, macrophages, Natural Killer (NK) cells, among others. These cells primarily function to regulate and impede tumor progression. However, as cancer progresses, the main function of these cells is modified, ultimately contributing to the promotion and expansion of the tumor^[16].

The most recent pathway by which TME contributes to tumor progression is the communication mediated by EVs. Tumor cells establish a bidirectional communication with TME components through EVs secretion. These EVs carry signaling molecules, oncogenic proteins and nucleic acids which contribute to tumorigenesis, tumor progression, invasion and metastasis^[16]. In PC, the predominant cellular elements constituting the TME include Cancer-Associated Fibroblast (CAFs), Pancreatic Stellate Cells (PSCs), Tumor-Associated Macrophages (TAMs), NK cells, Mesenchymal Stem Cells (MSCs), endothelial cells and Dendritic cells (DCs). Several studies have demonstrated that these TME cells could interact with the Pancreatic cancer cells (PCCs) through a bidirectional communication process mediated by EVs. This interaction is associated which increased tumor growth, tumor progression, angiogenesis, invasion and metastasis, chemoresistance and tumor immunity (Figure 3)^[7].

3.1. Cell proliferation and angiogenesis

As previously mentioned, the communication between PCCs and endothelial cells by EVs can promote tumor proliferation processes and the angiogenesis in PC (Table 1). Among the macromolecules contained in these EVs is myoferlin, a key protein expressed in PCCs-EXOs. This protein is known to be overexpressed in certain cancer types, although it is likewise expressed in EXOs derived from non-tumor cells. The research revealed that the incubation between endothelial cells (HUVEC) with EXOs isolated from PCCs significantly increased the proliferation and migration rates of HUVEC cells. However, when these endothelial cells were exposed with myoferlin-deficient EXOs, their proliferation and migration rates decreased significantly, hence showing a role for myoferlin in PC tumorigenesis^[17].

Another protein included in PCCs-EVs is ANXA1^[18]. The effect of ANXA1 and its association with PC were demonstrated by comparing EVs derived from PaCa-2 cells, which contain ANXA1, and EVs derived from KO-ANXA1 PaCa-2 cells. ANXA1 interacted with the Formyl peptide receptors (FPRs) on fibroblasts and endothelial cells. Results demonstrated that migration and invasion processes were more pronounced with ANXA1-EVs than with KO- ANXA1-EVs in fibroblasts, whereas if ANXA1 interacts with FPRs on endothelial cells led to an increase in the epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT). Notably, EMT plays a crucial role in the establishment of the neo vasculature during tumor angiogenesis, increasing factors such as Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor (VEGF), Smooth Muscle Actin (α SMA) or Fibroblast Activated Protein 1 (FAP1 α)^[18].

In addition to proteins, nucleic acids are also involved in the communication between TME and PCCs. Specifically, miR-27a is found to be overexpressed in PCCs-EXOs targeting endothelial cells. miR-27a interacts with and downregulates BTG2, a tumor suppressor gene, promoting the proliferation, invasion and angiogenesis, increasing VEGF expression, in endothelial cells^[19].

Conversely, PSCs-EXOs are enriched in miR-5703. miR-5703 has been demonstrated to target the 3'UTR region of the CMTM4 gene, resulting in reduced expression and consequently promoting the proliferation of PCCs. Recently, the role of CMTM4 as a tumor suppressor has been revealed. Overexpression of CMTM4 leads to down-regulation of PAK4, inhibiting PI3K/AKT pathway and the proliferation of PC cell lines^[20].

Similarly, it has been evidenced that hypoxia stimulates the overexpression of miR-4465 and miR-616-3p in PSCs-EXOs, targeting PCCs. Both miRNAs specifically recognize

PTEN mRNA and decrease its expression. Consequently, the activated AKT pathway promotes the proliferation of PCCs^[21].

3.2. Invasion and metastasis

In the same way, EVs and their cargo play a crucial role in triggering invasion and metastasis processes in PC. The liver emerges as the primary metastasis target organ in PC, with a prevalence of 41% compared to 13.9% for lung metastasis^[4].

Several factors enhance the process of PC metastasis to the liver (Table 1). Among them, the macrophage Migration Inhibitor Factor (MIF), overexpressed in PCCs-EXOs, stands out. MIF induces the release of TGF- β by Kupffer cells, leading the recruitment of bone marrow-derived macrophages and neutrophils to the liver, forming pre-metastatic niches. Furthermore, MIF inhibition has been shown to reduce the PC metastasis process to the liver^[22].

Recent findings demonstrate the role of Erzin, a protein implicated in the regulation of cell proliferation, morphogenesis, migration and adhesion, in promoting metastasis to the liver. Elevated expression of Erzin in EVs has been correlated with poor prognosis in PC patients. PCCs-EVs enriched with Erzin were linked to the polarization of TAM macrophages into M2 phenotype and contribute to liver metastatic processes^[23]. M2 macrophages have been associated with pro-tumor activity due to their ability to release anti-inflammatory factors such as TGF- β , involved in extracellular matrix remodeling and angiogenesis.

On the other hand, miR-501-3p overexpression in both PCCs and M2 TAM-derived EXOs promotes migration and invasion processes by PCCs, leading to tumor metastasis to liver and lungs in murine models. miR-501-3p inhibits the expression of TGFBR3 tumor suppressor gene through binding to its 3'UTR region, thereby activating the TGF- β growth factor signaling pathway^[24].

It is important to highlight the role of integrin $\alpha 6\beta 4$ (ITG $\alpha 6\beta 4$)-rich PCCs-derived EVs in PC metastasis to the lungs. The low expression of the Protein kinase D1 (PRKD1) in PC promotes the secretion of EVs enriched with ITG $\alpha 6\beta 4$. PRKD1 loss reduces the phosphorylation of its substrate, cortactin, resulting in increased levels of F-actin at the plasma membrane and enhanced secretion of EVs enriched in ITG $\alpha 6\beta 4$ to the lungs^[25].

Finally, it has been reported the existence of EXOs enriched with miR-21 secreted by PSCs. These EXOs induce migration and metastasis processes in PCCs by activating metalloproteinase 2/9 (MMP2/9) activity, which is involved in the EMT process as well as the Ras/ERK signaling pathway^[26].

3.3. Chemoresistance

Drug resistance is a general challenge in PC patients, even with the use of standard drugs like Gemcitabine, a deoxycytidine analog inhibiting DNA replication and repair^[27]. Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto. However, many PC patients develop resistance to this treatment^[28].

The investigation into the origins of this resistance revealed the involvement of the SNAI1 protein and its target, miR-146a. Gemcitabine treatment increased the secretion of SNAI1 and miR-146a-rich EXOs by CAFs. Consequently, these EXOs enhanced proliferation of the PC epithelial cells, along with resistance to Gemcitabine^[28]. To address this discovery, GW4869, a sphingomyelinase inhibitor which avoids EXOs formation and release, was employed leading to a decrease in tumor growth (Table 1)^[29]. Therefore, these results suggested that the combination of GW4869 with chemotherapy agents could be promising in future *in vivo* trials^[28].

Gemcitabine has also been associated with elevated expression of miR-106b in CAFs and CAF-derived EXOs. miR-106b targets the 3'UTR of the *TP53INP1* gene, inhibiting its expression and promoting chemoresistance in PCCs (Table 1). This gene has also been related to the development of chemoresistance in breast cancer. However, its molecular mechanism of action remains unknown^[30].

Continuous Gemcitabine exposure has been correlated to an increase EXOs secretion by CAFs targeting PCCs. Analysis of EXOs content identified five highly overexpressed miRNAs: miR-21, miR-181a, miR-221, miR-222 and miR-92a. These miRNAs collectively inhibit the expression of the tumor suppressor gene *PTEN* in recipient PCCs, thereby fostering promoting chemoresistance and tumor proliferation in PC^[31].

The role of PSCs-derived EVs, enriched with long non-coding RNA UCA1 (lncRNA UCA1), which target PCCs is noteworthy in the context of Gemcitabine resistance and tumorigenesis. Under hypoxic conditions, lncRNA UCA1 recruits the histone-lysine methyltransferase EZH2 in PCCs, promoting *SOCS3* gene inhibition through promoter methylation. Overexpression of *SOCS3* has been correlated with reduced tumor growth, metastasis and Gemcitabine resistance in both *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies^[32].

3.4. Tumor-associated immunity.

EVs play a crucial role in immunosuppression and immune evasion processes in PC. PCCs-derived EXOs have demonstrated the capacity to induce apoptosis in T lymphocytes through the activation of p38 MAPK-dependent signaling pathway. The activation of this kinase initiates stress activation in the endoplasmic reticle (ER),

triggering the apoptotic mechanism in lymphocytes through the PERK–eIF2 α –ATF4–CHOP signaling pathway^[33].

On the other hand, EVs derived from PCCs and directed towards NK cells contain elevated TGF- β (Table 1). Consequently, NK cells reduced the production of cytotoxicity factors and cytokines such as NKG2D, CD107a, IFN- γ , CD71, CD98 and 2-NBDG. This study suggests that the activation of TGF β 1- Smad2/3 signaling pathway is responsible for NK cell dysfunction^[34].

4. EVs as diagnostic and prognostic markers in Pancreatic Cancer.

Nowadays, the unique diagnostic biomarker approved by FDA in PC is CA19-9^[35]. CA19-9 is a surface carbohydrate highly expressed in PC, which is anchored with an amount of membrane proteins such as mucins or surrounding apolipoproteins^[36]. Despite its efficacy in detecting PC with a sensitivity 70-80%, CA19-9 is somewhat nonspecific because elevated levels are also found in other pathologies such as cholestasis, diabetes mellitus^[35], biliary obstructions, pancreatitis and liver diseases^[36].

Furthermore, not all the PC patients exhibit elevated levels of this marker^[36]. Due to its limited specificity, researchers are actively pursuing alternative markers, as well as combinations of markers, to enhance the precision and efficacy of PC diagnosis (Table 2). The subsequent classification of diagnostic and prognostic markers for PC is based on the nature of the molecule targeted: protein, RNA or DNA.

4.1. Protein biomarkers.

EVs contain numerous protein-based molecules that have the potential to serve as diagnostic and prognostic markers in PC. A notable example is the epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR), which has been found to be overexpressed in EVs derived from PCCs^[37]. Comparative studies analyzing expression of EGFR and CA19-9 in healthy individuals and PC patients revealed that EVs enriched with EGFR were 35 times more prevalent in PC patients than in healthy individuals. Notably, EVs enriched with CA19-9 were 130 times more abundant in PC cohort in comparison to healthy population. However, it's important to note the relatively small sample size in these studies, consisting of 6 healthy volunteers and 5 patients with PC, leading to heterogeneous results within the PC patient group^[37].

Another potential diagnostic and prognostic marker is glypican-1 (GPC1), a membrane proteoglycan abundant in EXOs derived from PCCs^[38]. Elevated levels of GPC1 in EXOs from PCCs have been associated to angiogenesis and metastasis processes in PC^[39]. Melo *et al.* (2015) demonstrated that the presence of circulating GPC1⁺ EXOs

(GPC1⁺crEXOs) in serum of PC patients allows distinguishing between healthy donors and PC patients, as well as between early or late-stage patients. Furthermore, this study identified the presence of KRAS^{G12D}, one of the most frequent mutations in PC patients, within these GPC1⁺crEXOs^[38]. However, conflicting results were observed in other studies, where the level of GPC1⁺crExo in plasma did not significantly distinguish between healthy individuals and those with PC^[40]. Notably, Melo *et al.*'s study had larger cohort (n=246 patients with CP) compared the present study (n=27 patients with CP)^[40], potentially influencing the results. Despite this, they concluded that the level of GPC1⁺crExo in plasma allowed them to determine tumor size and to distinguish between patients who underwent tumor resection and those who did not. It should be noted that the quantification and detection methodology used by Melo *et al.* might be more complex for clinical reproducibility^[40].

The potential prognostic value of GPC1⁺ EXOs has also been studied for predicting Advanced Pancreatic Cancer (APC). Plasma levels of GPC1⁺ EXOs were significantly higher in APC patients than in healthy donors. Remarkably, APC patients treated with Regional Intra-Arterial Chemotherapy (RIAC) presented significantly decreased levels of GPC1⁺ EXOs and a higher survival rate. This fact suggests that low level of GPC1⁺ EXOs could serve as a prognostic marker to predict the outcome of RIAC treatment in PC patients^[41].

Eph type A2 receptor (EphA2) is a novel and promising candidate for becoming a PC marker. This receptor, overexpressed in several tumors including pancreatic and esophageal, is associated with tumor progression and metastasis processes^[14]. Enriched in EphA2 PCCs-derived EVs purified from plasma have demonstrated remarkable capabilities in distinguishing between PC patients and healthy donors, achieving a sensitivity of 94%. In addition, it effectively distinguished between early and late stages with a sensitivity of 91%. Thus, EphA2 outperformed CA19-9 significantly ($p < 0.001$), which had an 81% reliability in discriminating between patients with chronic pancreatitis (CP) and healthy individuals^[14].

Another potential diagnostic marker under exploration is ZIP4, a zinc transporter present in plasma cells, endosomes and EVs membranes^[42]. Increased ZIP4 levels have been linked to the development of several cancers including pancreatic, lung and hepatic cancers. Jin *et al.* demonstrated, through *in vitro* and *in vivo* assays, that PCCs derived-EVs with high levels of ZIP4 can promote proliferation and migration in PC. Investigating the potential diagnostic value of ZIP4, significant differences in ZIP4 levels were found between patients with malignant pancreatic cancer (MP) and healthy donors, MP and patients with benign pancreatic diseases (BP), and MP and patients with biliary diseases.

Furthermore, the diagnostic efficacy of ZIP4 was further confirmed by the area under the curve (AUC) values, which confirmed its efficacy to distinguish between MP patients and healthy individuals (AUC = 0.8931) and between MP and BP (AUC = 0.89)^[42].

4.2. RNA biomarkers

Beyond protein analysis, exploring the RNA content of EVs opens avenues for comprehensive studies. In the context of PC, several RNA types play crucial roles, with a particular focus on lncRNA and miRNA.

4.2.1. Long non-coding RNA.

lncRNA are long-stranded non-coding RNA with more than 200 nucleotides. They commonly have a regulatory role in gene expression and they have been linked to the development of certain pathologies such as PC^[43].

Highly Up-regulated in Liver Cancer (HULC) is englobed among these lncRNAs. Its expression has been linked to the EMT phenomenon. The action of HULC induces phenotypic alterations in PCCs, including the reduction in the expression of E-cadherin, characteristic of epithelial cells, and increased levels of N-cadherin, vimentin or SNAI1, which are typical of mesenchymal cells^[43].

Recently, it has been discovered that TGF- β can induce the EMT process and lead to the appearance and overexpression of HULC in PC cells. Furthermore, PCCs-derived EVs enriched in HULC promote the EMT phenomenon in recipient cells. This induction manifests as increased expression of N-cadherin, vimentin and SNAI1, thereby enhancing invasion, migration and tumor growth in the recipient cells^[43].

Moreover, HULC role as a possible PC diagnostic biomarker has been tested. The results showed its capability to distinguish between PC patients and non-PC patients with an AUC of 0.92. It is important to highlight that non-PC patients included healthy donors and patients with IPMN (Intraductal Papillary Mucinous Neoplasms). Additionally, the study's sample size was relatively small (n=20 for PC patients), suggesting the need for larger-scale studies to validate its role as a diagnostic biomarker for PC^[43].

4.2.2. microRNAs

miRNAs are small, non-coding RNAs with the capacity to modulate several physiological and pathological processes, including cancer, by repressing mRNA translation^[39]. Several miRNAs are notably overexpressed in PCCs-derived EVs. Lai *et al.* identified five miRNAs (miR-10b, miR-21, miR-30c, miR-181a and miR-let7a) with elevated expression in PCCs-EVs, allowing for a significant differentiation between PC patients and healthy donors, achieving 100% specificity and sensitivity with an AUC of 1. This

discrimination is also observed when comparing PC patients with those suffering from chronic pancreatitis (CP). The inclusion of CP patients was necessary due to the complexity of distinguishing between both pathologies using diagnostic markers^[39].

To assess the reliability of the aforementioned miRNAs compared to GPC1 and CA19-9, the AUC for both markers was estimated. The AUC for GPC1 was 0.75, which was not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$), while CA19-9 showed a sensitivity of 87% and an AUC of 0.92. Furthermore, in contrast to the levels of GPC1-rich EVs, the levels of EXOs rich in these miRNAs decreased significantly at 24 hours after resection. On the other hand, the levels of CA19-9-rich EXOs were found to be highly variable and thus inconclusive^[39]. These data collectively suggest that the use of miR-10b, miR-21, miR-30c, miR-181a and miR-let7a as diagnostic markers is more reliable than the use of GPC1 or CA19-9.

Chen *et al.* recently proposed the use of miR-451a-enriched EVs as a potential diagnostic marker for PC. Their study yielded compelling results, demonstrating that miR-451a is significantly overexpressed in PC patients, effectively differentiating between PC patients ($n=191$) and healthy individuals ($n=90$), with an AUC of 0.896. Additionally, miR-451a can distinguish PC patients from those with benign pancreatic disease (BP) ($n=95$), with an AUC of 0.855^[44].

Furthermore, the levels of miR-451a in serum EVs of PC patients exhibited a positive correlation with the metastatic grade of the tumor. Notably, the levels of miR-451a decreased in patients who underwent chemotherapy or surgery. These findings suggest that miR-451a may serve not only as a diagnostic marker for PC but also as a prognostic indicator, as its levels are sensitive to both the tumor stage and the effects of anticancer therapies^[44].

4.3. DNA biomarkers.

Numerous gene mutations, including mutations in the *KRAS* oncogene and the *TP53* tumor suppressor gene, have been linked to a positive diagnosis of PC^[45]. Predominantly, mutations in codons 12 (G12D and G12V) and 13 of the *KRAS* oncogene are the most prevalent. Because *KRAS* is involved in the RAF/MEK/MAPK and PI3K/PTEN/AKT pathways, these mutations lead to the hyperactivated cell division, thereby promoting tumor development and maintenance. Furthermore, *KRAS* has been implicated in the rewiring of glucose metabolism, as it can enhance glucose uptake, glycolysis and lactate transport, a phenomenon known as the Warburg effect^[45].

Clinical studies have explored whether the detection of mutations in the *KRAS* and *TP53* genes from EVs can serve as diagnostic markers in PC^[46,47]. Yang *et al.* confirmed the

presence of EXOs with the *KRAS*^{G12D} mutation in various groups, including healthy individuals (2.6%), patients with CP (55.6%), individuals with IPMN-type lesions (28.6%), and in PC patients (39.6%). While the percentage of patients with *KRAS*^{G12D} is higher in those with PC, it's essential to emphasize the relatively low number of individuals in the healthy group (n=9) compared to the larger PC group (n=48). For this reason, is challenging to use the presence of this mutation as diagnostic marker for PC, given its presence in all the groups studied^[46].

The reduced specificity of *KRAS* mutations for the diagnosis of PC was further underscored in another study analyzing the percentage of mutations in codons 12 and 13 of the *KRAS* gene among individuals with localized PC, locally advanced PC and metastatic PC. In this study, mutations were observed in all groups, including healthy individuals (7.4%), those with localized PC (66.7%), locally advanced PC (80%), and metastatic PC (85%)^[47].

On the other hand, the potential role of the mutated *TP53* as a diagnostic marker for PC was also investigated. Specifically, the *TP53*^{R273H} mutation was examined in EVs from healthy individuals, patients with CP, individuals with IPMN lesions and PC patients. The results confirmed the absence of this mutation in the first two groups (healthy individuals and those with PC), while it was present in patients with IPMN lesions (28.6%) and in PC patients (4.2%)^[46]. However, as before, the sample size may impact the results^[47]. Therefore, further exploration of the role of *TP53*^{R273H} as a predictive marker for PC in EVs necessitates larger-scale clinical studies.

5. EVs as therapeutic agents

The utility of EVs extends beyond diagnosis and prognosis; they are also emerging as potent tools in therapeutics applications. The aim is to take advantage of them as natural carrier systems due to their role in cellular communication during both physiological and pathological processes^[48]. Recent studies have shown that EVs offer several advantages over other *in vivo* therapy delivery methods, such as liposomes or nanoparticles, making them highly promising for therapeutic purposes^[49,50].

Among these advantages highlight their extraordinary *in vivo* stability, attribute to their natural composition and reduced immunological clearance^[51]. In fact, several studies have demonstrated that repeated administration of EXOs does not cause signs of toxicity or immunogenicity. Their high delivery efficiency is another strength, with the ability to bind specifically to target cells or tissues via receptors, facilitating controlled release into the corresponding target structures^[51]. Characterized by excellent transcellular

permeability and a variety of release mechanisms including phagocytosis, macropinocytosis, interactions with lipid rafts, caveolae, receptor-mediated endocytosis, clathrin interactions and direct fusion, EVs offer versatile options for therapeutic delivery^[52]. Additionally, their ability to traverse the blood-brain barrier, thanks to their small size and biocompatible structure, positions them as valuable carriers, especially considering the limitations most drugs face in penetrating the brain^[51].

A particularly promising aspect is the potential for highly targeted therapies. EVs from different cell types exhibit an inherent affinity for specific recipient cells, enhancing drug concentration in particular tissues, such as tumors or specific organs^[53]. This targeted delivery approach allows for a reduction in drug dosage, minimizing toxicity in non-target organs. This phenomenon is influenced by the tissue tropism of EVs, which depends on the expression of specific adhesion molecules. Recent research indicates that alterations in the abundance and identity of tetraspanins and integrins on EVs contributes to changes in molecular interactions with recipient cells, thereby influencing their *in vivo* functions^[54].

Another crucial factor in this regard is the "homing" phenomenon, wherein cells exhibit a preference for targeting tissues harboring their progenitor cells, often observed in autologous EVs. Recent studies have shed light on this phenomenon, noting that small EVs expressing tetraspanin-8 display enhanced uptake by the pancreas and lungs, in contrast to the liver and intestine^[54]. While the precise mechanisms controlling tropisms in pancreas are not yet fully elucidated, it has been suggested that an increase in KRAS-induced oncogenic macropinocytosis in PC may play a pivotal role^[55,56]. Furthermore, the possibility of modifying the EV surface through genetic engineering, including the addition of specific peptide ligands to bind to particular tissues or cells, is underway^[57]. Techniques are also being developed to load EXOs with specific proteins, such as those containing ubiquitination signals that guide them to the endosomal system and efficiently trap them into EXOs^[58].

However, the primary challenge in effectively employing EVs for the treatment of various conditions, including cancer, lies in the standardization of the EV isolation methodologies, the optimization of the cargo amounts due to size variability, and the challenges associated with large-scale production^[59]. In this context, significant research has been conducted, including studies aiming to generate EXOs and load them with siRNA on a large scale using MSCs in bioreactor systems^[60].

Another difficulty in the therapeutic administration of EVs is their rapid clearance from circulation, leading to accumulation in organs like the liver, spleen and lungs, as

evidenced by previous studies^[52]. To address these limitations, significant efforts are being made to develop artificial EXOs^[61] or to modify them to extend their half-life in circulation^[62].

Currently, several potential applications of EVs in the treatment of PC have been proposed, focusing on critical aspects of this disease^[61]. These include: inhibiting tumor growth, overcoming drug resistance and chemoresistance, modifying the tumor immune microenvironment and targeting mutation-specific therapies (such as those related to *KRAS* gene)^[62–64].

Since EVs play a crucial role in tumor progression, chemotherapy resistance, metastasis formation, among others, inhibiting tumor cell-to-tumor cell communication via EVs is emerging as a potential solution against PC. Strategies are being explored to block both the release of EVs, as mentioned earlier with the use of GW4869^[65,66], and to interfere with the entry of these EVs into recipient cells by modifying or blocking adhesion and recognition molecules between EVs and target cells^[67,68]. This approach holds promise for preventing metastasis, given the involvement of EVs in the preparation of the metastatic niche.

Furthermore, EVs are perceived as promising vehicles for loading drugs and therapeutic molecules, taking advantage of their function as natural messengers^[69]. In this context, the strategy of introducing chemotherapeutic agents into EVs is being developed, aiming to combat the tumor from within^[69]. Paclitaxel, a drug affecting the cytoskeleton and causing mitotic arrest of tumor cells, has been successfully used in this approach^[70]. Recent studies demonstrate that MSC-derived EVs can package and release paclitaxel, resulting in an anticancer effect with potent antiproliferative activity in human PCCs^[69]. Similarly, investigations involving heterologous EXOs derived from MSCs loaded with gemcitabine or paclitaxel have demonstrated *in vitro* effects on both pancreatic cell lines and MiaPaCa-2 cell xenografts. Additional studies with autologous exosomes generated from PC cell lines and loaded with gemcitabine and evaluated on themselves and in Panc-1 xenograft models, have yielded similar promising results. These studies highlight the effectiveness of drug delivery through EVs, surpassing conventional drug delivery demonstrating the capability to induce tumor regression in nude mouse models^[61].

In addition, EVs offer a versatile platform for loading various therapeutic molecules for PC treatment: miRNAs, small interfering RNA (siRNA) and hairpin RNA (shRNA)^[59,71]. Their effects included reducing tumor growth, acting on proliferation, apoptosis, migration, invasion, growth velocity and angiogenesis^[71]. Studies in this field have used EVs loaded with miRNA inhibitors, both from MSCs and macrophages (heterologous)

and autologous PC lines, demonstrating their impact in PC cell lines and xenograft models. Notable examples of miRNA-loaded EVs for the treatment of PC include miR-1231, miR-126-3p, miR-145-5p, miR-501-3p, miR-27a and miR-125b-5p^[61].

Regarding drug resistance, there is increasing evidence that EXOs play a crucial role in actively transporting chemotherapeutic agents out of cancer cells, either directly or indirectly^[72]. Studies with EVs loaded with inhibitors of resistance-related miRNAs, both, synthesized by both resistant PC cells themselves and cells in the tumor microenvironment, such as stromal cells (CAFs) or macrophages, have been pursued. Strategies include inhibition of miR-155, miR-146b, miR-106b, miR-365 and miR-210, all linked to gemcitabine resistance^[61]. Another approach explores combining gemcitabine in EVs with miRNA or molecules that decrease resistance generation, such as Survivin-T34A or EphA2, to increase drug sensitivity^[73].

Another therapeutic method for PC involves leveraging siRNA targeting mutations in the *KRAS* gene, particularly the extensively studied *KRAS*^{G12D} mutation. EVs designed to carry siRNAs specific against *KRAS*^{G12D} have demonstrated efficacy, leading to a decrease in tumor size^[73]. This innovative approach has progressed to a phase I clinical trial, currently under development, holding promise for positive outcomes^[74].

Modifying the immune microenvironment is another crucial strategy in PC treatment^[7]. In the early stages, the immune system activates innate and adaptive immune responses against PC tumor cells^[75]. However, immune pressure leads to phenotypic selection of PCCs, resulting in loss of their immunogenicity and the induction of immune tolerance, a phenomenon known as tumor immunoediting. Strategies to reactivate the immune response in PC include using of immunomodulators such as STING agonists (activators of the interferon gene stimulator pathway) in immunotherapy^[75]. Studies with PC-derived EVs have revealed the antitumor effect of these agonists when administered via EVs, associated with an increase in proliferative CD8⁺ T cells^[76]. Inhibiting miR-301a-3p secreted by PCCs suppresses macrophage conversion to the M2 phenotype. Notably, EXOs loaded with miR-155 and miR-125b-2 have been observed to reverse the M2 phenotype to M1, thus stimulating the immune system^[63].

Conclusions

Decreasing PC mortality rate is a clear unmet medical need today. The absence of early symptoms, coupled with aggressive growth and premature dissemination, results in 80%

of patients being diagnosed at advanced stages, often with distant metastases that render their disease surgically inoperable. To improve prognosis and diminish the mortality, early diagnostic tools for PC are urgently needed.

EVs are attracting attention recently for their potential as carriers of biomarkers in cancer. All cell types are capable of secreting EVs, pivotal in cell-cell communication by packaging and delivering bioactive constituents that influence the physiology of target cells. These “educational elements” can contribute to tumor growth and expansion. Therefore, beyond carrying characteristic tumor molecules, blocking their release or uptake by target cells represents a viable strategy to decelerate tumor growth.

Despite the expectations for EV-based therapy for PC are tremendously high, further research is required to develop a more proactive approach. Successfully translating these strategies into clinical practice requires to minimize costs, to standardize protocols for rapid and reproducible applications and building on validated clinical trial data. This meticulous work is indispensable to ensure that these innovative approaches enhance therapeutic outcomes for patients with PC.

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Conflicts of Interest

All authors declared that there are no conflicts of interest.

Figure Legends:

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the biogenesis of EVs. A) EXOs derive from the endosomal pathway, in which, after a process of membrane invagination, an ESE is formed (1). After maturation, it becomes an LSE (2), which subsequently leads to the formation of an MVB with ILVs or future EXOs inside (3). These MVBs have three possible destinations: fusion with the plasma membrane, releasing the EXOs to the extracellular medium (4); fusion with autophagosomes (5); or fusion with lysosomes (6). MVs derive from the evagination of the plasma membrane (7). **B)** Apoptotic bodies are released during the apoptotic process of cells. Figure created with Biorender.

Figure 2. Methods for isolation of EVs from biological fluids. The most commonly used techniques are based on isolation by density (UC, DG); by size (UF, FFF, exclusion chromatography); by precipitation (hydrophilic polymers, organic solvents and commercial kits); by affinity (WB, ELISA, affinity chromatography); and with microfluidic devices. Figure created with Biorender.

Figure 3: EVs as mediators of the communication between PCCs and TME in PC. The content of EVs derived from PC and from TME cells are capable to modulate PC progression. Pancreatic cancer cells (PCCs), pancreatic stellate cells (PSCs), tumor-associated fibroblasts (CAFs), tumor-associated macrophages (TAMs), NK cells, endothelial cells and dendritic cells (DCs). Figure created with Biorender.

Figure 4. Workflow of the process of isolation and characterization of EVs for their application in PC diagnostics. This figure contains all the points discussed throughout the work, i.e., sampling by liquid biopsy, isolation and characterization of EVs, detection and quantification of their markers, and their application in the diagnosis and prognosis of PC. Figure created with Biorender.

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